

STRUCTURAL MODIFICATION OF EXOPOLYSACCHARIDE BY *RHIZOBIUM RADIOBACTER* 36

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Bacteria of the *Rhizobium* genus are also well-known for their ability to synthesize exopolysaccharides (EPS), which are crucial for their survival and function under abiotic stress conditions [1]. The synthesis and regulation of EPS in *Rhizobium* are governed by specific gene clusters, most notably the *exo* genes [2].

Rhizobium's ability to produce EPS helps it survive abiotic stress and support symbiotic relationships. Understanding EPS structure, function, and regulation by *exo* genes highlights their importance in ecosystems and applied sciences. Recent EPS research offers new possibilities in biotechnology, including sustainable agriculture, environmental remediation, and crop stress management. In this study, the synthesis and structural modification of EPS by *R. radiobacter* 36, isolated from soybean (*Glycine max* L.), were investigated.

GC-MS analysis revealed that EPS of *R. radiobacter* 36 consists of 88.053% Glucose and 11.947% Galactose in a molar ratio of 7.36:1. This structure differed from reported until now structures of EPS of rhizobia. Salt stress not only impacted the expression of *exo* genes but also significantly altered the structure of synthesized EPS. FTIR analysis revealed distinctive features that provide insights into their structural complexity. The O-H stretching vibrations, ranging from 3281.21 to 3288.58 cm^{-1} , indicate hydrogen-bonded hydroxyl groups, crucial for the structural stability of EPS [3, 4]. Strong hydrogen bonding around 3280 cm^{-1} suggests a compact polysaccharide network crucial for gel formation. **Non-hydrogen-bonded hydroxyl groups are free and available** to interact with other species, including metal cations like Na^+ . Since these hydroxyl groups are not engaged in internal hydrogen bonding, their oxygen atoms can **donate electron density** to coordinate with and stabilize sodium ions. With increasing NaCl concentration, the number of available non-hydrogen-bonded hydroxyl groups, as assumed, decreased due to binding with Na^+ ions. Non-hydrogen-bonded hydroxyl groups were detected by FT-IR only in the absence of NaCl (3751.15 cm^{-1} at 0%) and at 0.5% NaCl (3853.45 cm^{-1}). **In the presence of excess Na^+ ions (1.0, 1.5, 2.0 and 2.5% NaCl), non-hydrogen-bonded hydroxyl groups may disappear from FT-IR spectra** because they are engaged in binding with Na^+ and thus **are no longer detectable as free –OH groups**.

The glycoside linkage (C-O-C) peaks at 891.45–927.41 cm^{-1} confirm the polymerized structure typical of microbial polysaccharides [5]. Several bands in the 920–840 cm^{-1} region suggest the presence of both α and β configurations [4]. These linkages offer stability, rigidity and water solubility, suggesting the EPS can form a durable structural matrix, resistant to environmental degradation [4]. This finding suggests that the bacterial strain *R. radiobacter* 36 also strives to synthesize an EPS structure with enhanced stability and rigidity in response to salinity. The carbohydrate ring vibrations (614.68 to 815.13 cm^{-1}) further corroborate the polysaccharide nature of the EPS [3]. This evidence suggest that salt stress induces structural modifications of EPS of *R. radiobacter* 36.

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